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TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS), also known as “patches,” are dosage forms designed to deliver a therapeutically effective amount of drug across a patient’s skin. It’s a desirable form of drug delivery because of the obvious advantages e.g. convenient and pain-free self-administration for patients, avoidance of hepatic first. The first commercially available prescription patch was approved by the U.S. Food and drug administration in December 1979, which administered scopolamine for motion sickness. This review article covers brief outline advantages, skin pathways for transdermal drug delivery systems (TDDS), various components of transdermal patch, and approaches for preparation of transdermal patches, evaluation of transdermal system, general clinical considerations in the use of transdermal drug delivery systems and limitation of transdermal drug delivery systems.

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INTRODUCTION:[1-5]

The most common form of drug delivery is the oral route. In this route of administration has notable advantages and also have significant drawbacks like first pass metabolism, drug degradation in gastrointestinal tract due to enzymes, pH etc. To overcome these difficulties a Novel drug delivery system was developed. These factors as well as other factors such as repetitive dosing and unpredictable absorption, led to the concept of the controlled drug delivery system or therapeutic system. The primary objectives of controlled drug delivery are to ensure safety and to improve efficacy of drugs as well as patient compliance. Transdermal drug delivery is defined as self contained, discrete dosage forms which, when applied to the intact skin, deliver the drug, through the skin at controlled rate to the systemic circulation. Transdermal drug delivery system (TDDS) established itself as an integral part of novel drug delivery systems. They provide controlled continuous delivery of drugs through the skin to the systemic circulation. The drug is mainly delivered through the skin with the aid of transdermal patch. A Transdermal patch is a medicament adhesive patch that is placed on the skin to deliver a specific dose of medication through the skin and into the bloodstream. A drug is applied in a relatively high dose to the inside of a patch, which is worn on the skin for an extended period of time. Through a diffusion process, the drug enters the bloodstream directly through the skin via three pathways-through hair follicles, through sebaceous glands, through sweat duct.. Since there is high concentration in the patch and low concentration in the blood, the drug will keep diffusing into the blood for a long period of time, maintaining the constant concentration of drug in the blood flow.

Advantages[6-7]

1. self administration is possible and continuous, sustained release of drug.
2. Multiday dosing interval
3. Avoids first pass hepatic metabolism and enzymatic degradation by GIT.
4. Less frequent dosing improves patient compliance.
5. Alternate route for patients who are unable to take oral medications
6. Dose delivery unaffected by vomiting or diarrhea.
7. Drug administration stops with patch removal.

Disadvantages[6-7]

1. Only small, lipophilic drugs can be delivered currently through the skin
2. Not suitable for high drug doses.
3. Adhesion may vary with patch type and environmental conditions.
4. Skin irritation and hypersensitivity reactions may occur.
5. The barrier function of the skin changes from one site to another on the same person, from person to person and with age.

PHYSIOLOGY OF THE SKIN:[8]

Skin is one of the most extensive organ of the body covering an area of about 2m² on in an average human adult. This multilayered organ receives approximately one third of all blood circulating through the body. With thickness of only a millimeter, the skin separates the underlying blood circulation network from outside environment. Human skin comprises of three distinct but mutually dependent tissues:

- A) The stratified, vascular, cellular epidermis,
- B) Underlying dermis of connective tissues and
- C) Hypodermis.

Epidermis:

It results from an active epithelial basal cell population and is approximately 150 micrometer thick. It is the outermost layer of skin and process of differentiation results in migration of cells from basal layer towards the skin surface. The end result of this process is the formation of a thin, stratified and extremely resilient layer(the stratum corneum) at the skin surface.

Stratum corneum: This is the outermost layer of skin, also called horny layer. It is approximately 10 mm thick when dry but swells to several times this thickness when fully hydrated. It contains 10 to 25 layers of parallel to the skin surface, lying dead, keratinized cells, called corneocytes. It is flexible but relatively impermeable. The stratum corneum is the principal barrier for penetration. The barrier nature of the horny layer depends critically on its constituents: 75 to 80% proteins, 5 to 15% lipids, and 5 to 10% undecylenol material on a dry weight basis. Protein fractions predominantly contain alpha-keratin (70%) with some beta-keratin (10%) and cell envelope (5%). Lipid constituents vary with body site (neutral lipids, sphingolipids, polar lipids, cholesterol). Phospholipids are largely absent, a unique feature of mammalian membrane.

Viable epidermis: This is situated beneath the stratum corneum and varies in thickness from 0.06 mm on the eyelids to 0.8 mm on the palms.

Dermis:

Electron microscopic examination shows that the dermis is made up of a network of robust collagen fibers of fairly uniform thickness with regularly spaced cross striations. It is about 3 to 5 mm and contains the blood vessels, lymph vessels, and nerves. It also provide oxygen and nutrients to the skin while removing toxins and waste products.

Hypodermis:

The hypodermis or subcutaneous fat tissue supports the dermis and epidermis. It serves as a fat storage area. This layer helps to regulate temperature, provides nutritional support and mechanic protection. It carries principal blood vessels and nerves to skin and may contain sensory pressure organs. For transdermal drug delivery, the drug has to penetrate through all these three layers and reach into systemic circulation while in case of topical drug delivery, only penetration through stratum corneum is essential and then retention of drug in skin layers is desired.

Fig.1. Anatomy of skin represents different parts.

SKIN PATHWAYS FOR TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS:[9-12]

When drugs are applied on the skin surface, penetration into and through the skin can occur via various routes. Drugs penetrate either via the stratum corneum (transepidermal) or via the appendages (transappendageal). During penetration through the stratum corneum, two possible routes can be distinguished, Penetration alternating through the corneocytes and the lipid lamellae (transcellular route) and ii) Penetration along the tortuous pathway along the lipid lamellae (intercellular route).

Fig.2. Possible pathways for permeation of drug across the skin barrier.

Generally it is accepted that the predominant route of penetration through the stratum corneum is the intercellular route. This is mainly caused by the densely cross-linked cornified envelope coating the keratinocytes. However transcellular transport for small hydrophilic molecules such as water cannot completely be excluded. The appendage route or shunt route includes either the duct of the eccrine sweat glands or the follicular duct. The content of the eccrine sweat glands is mainly hydrophilic, while the content of the follicular duct is lipophilic. This is mainly due to the sebum excreted into the opening of the follicular duct. It is generally accepted that due to its large surface area, passive skin permeation mainly occurs through intact stratum corneum.

KINETICS OF TRANSDERMAL PERMEATION[13]

Knowledge of skin permeation kinetics is vital to the successful development of transdermal therapeutic systems. Transdermal permeation of a drug involves the following steps:

1. Sorption by stratum corneum.
2. Penetration of drug through viable epidermis.
3. Uptake of the drug by the capillary network in the dermal papillary layer.

This permeation can be possible only if the drug possesses certain physiochemical properties. The rate of permeation across the skin is given by:

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = P_s (C_d - C_r) \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where C_d and C_r are the concentration of the skin penetrant in the donor compartment i.e. on the surface of stratum corneum and in the receptor compartment i.e. body respectively. P_s is the overall permeability coefficient of the skin tissue to the penetrant. This permeability coefficient is given by the relationship:

$$P_s = \frac{K_s D_{ss}}{h_s} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

where K_s is the partition coefficient for the interfacial partitioning of the penetrant molecule from a solution medium or a transdermal therapeutic system on to the stratum corneum, D_{ss} is the apparent diffusivity for the steady state diffusion of the penetrant molecule through a thickness of skin tissues and h_s is the overall thickness of skin tissues. As K_s , D_{ss} and h_s are constant under given conditions the permeability coefficient P_s for a skin penetrant can be considered to be constant. From equation (1) it is clear that a constant rate of drug permeation can be obtained only when $C_d \gg C_r$ i.e. the drug concentration at the surface of the stratum corneum C_d is consistently and substantially greater than the drug concentration in the body C_r . The equation becomes:

$$\frac{dQ}{dt} = P_s C_d \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

And the rate of skin permeation is constant provided the magnitude of C_d remains fairly constant throughout the course of skin permeation. For keeping C_d constant the drug should be released from the device at a rate R_r i.e. either constant or greater than the rate of skin uptake R_a i.e. $R_r \gg R_a$.

Since $R_r \gg R_a$, the drug concentration on the skin surface C_d is maintained at a level equal to or greater than the equilibrium solubility of the drug in the stratum corneum C_s i.e. $C_d \gg C_s$. Therefore a maximum rate of skin permeation is obtained and is given by the equation:

$$(dQ/dt)_m = P_s C_s \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

From the above equation it can be seen that the maximum rate of skin permeation depends upon the skin permeability coefficient P_s and is equilibrium solubility in the stratum corneum C_s . Thus skin permeation appears to be stratum corneum limited.

FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY:[14]**Biological factors include:**

1. Skin condition
2. Skin age
3. Blood flow
4. Regional skin sites
5. Skin metabolism
6. Species differences

Physiological factors include:

1. Skin hydration
2. Temperature and pH
3. Diffusion coefficient
4. Drug concentration
5. Partition coefficient
6. Molecular size and shape

BASIC COMPONENTS OF TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS:

The components of transdermal devices include:[15-17]

1. Polymer matrix or matrices.
2. The drug
3. Permeation enhancers
4. Other excipients

Polymer Matrix

The Polymer controls the release of the drug from the device.

Possible useful polymers for transdermal devices are:

Natural Polymers:

e.g. Cellulose derivatives, Zein, Gelatin, Shellac, Waxes, Proteins, Gums and their derivatives, Natural rubber, Starch etc.

Synthetic Elastomers:

e.g. Polybutadiene, Hydrin rubber, Polysiloxane, Silicone rubber, Nitrile, Acrylonitrile, Butyl rubber, Styrenebutadiene rubber, Neoprene etc.

Synthetic Polymers:

e.g. Polyvinyl alcohol, Polyvinyl chloride, Polyethylene, Polypropylene, Polyacrylate, Polyamide, Polyurea, Polyvinylpyrrolidone, Polymethylmethacrylate, Epoxy etc.

Drug

For successfully developing a transdermal drug delivery system, the drug should be chosen with great care. The following are some of the desirable properties of a drug for transdermal delivery.

Physicochemical properties

1. The drug should have a molecular weight less than approximately 1000 daltons.
2. The drug should have affinity for both – lipophilic and hydrophilic phases. Extreme partitioning characteristics are not conducive to successful drug delivery via the skin.
3. The drug should have low melting point. Along with these properties the drug should be potent, having short half life and be non irritating.

Biological Properties:

1. The drug should be potent with a daily dose of the order of a few mg/day.
2. The half life ($t_{1/2}$) of the drug should be short.
3. The drug must not induce a cutaneous irritation or allergic response.
4. Drugs, which degrade in the GI tract or are inactivated by hepatic first-pass effect, are suitable candidates for Transdermal delivery.
5. Tolerance to the drug must not develop under the near zero-order release profile of Transdermal delivery.
6. Drugs, which have to be administered for a long period of time or which cause adverse effects to non-target tissues can also, be formulated for Transdermal delivery.

Permeation Enhancers

These are compounds which promote skin permeability by altering the skin as a barrier to the flux of a desired penetrant. These may conveniently be classified under the following main headings:

Solvents

These compounds increase penetration possibly by swelling the polar pathway and/or by fluidizing lipids. Examples include water alcohols – methanol and ethanol; alkyl methyl sulfoxides – dimethyl sulfoxide, alkyl homologs of methyl sulfoxide dimethyl acetamide and dimethyl formamide; pyrrolidones – 2 pyrrolidone, N-methyl, 2-pyrrolidone; laurocapram (Azone), miscellaneous solvents – propylene glycol, glycerol, silicone fluids, isopropyl palmitate.

Surfactants

These compounds are proposed to enhance polar pathway transport, especially of hydrophilic drugs. The ability of a surfactant to alter penetration is a function of the polar head group and the hydrocarbon chain length.

Anionic Surfactants: e.g. Dioctyl sulphosuccinate, Sodium lauryl sulphate, Decylmethyl sulphoxide etc.

Nonionic Surfactants: e.g. Pluronic F127, Pluronic F68, etc.

Bile Salts: e.g. Sodium taurocholate, Sodium deoxycholate, Sodium tauroglycocholate.

Biary system: These systems apparently open up the heterogeneous multilaminar pathway as well as the continuous pathways. e.g. Propylene glycol-oleic acid and 1, 4-butane diol-linoleic acid.

Miscellaneous chemicals

These include urea, a hydrating and keratolytic agent; N, N-dimethyl-m-toluamide; calcium thioglycolate; anticholinergic agents. Some potential permeation enhancers have recently been described but the available data on their effectiveness sparse. These include eucalyptol, di-o-methyl- β -cyclodextrin and soyabean casein.

Other Excipients: Adhesives:

The fastening of transdermal devices to the skin has so far been done by using a pressure sensitive adhesive. The pressure sensitive adhesive can be positioned on the face of the device or in the back of the device and extending peripherally.

Both adhesive systems should fulfill the following criteria.

1. Should not irritate or sensitize the skin or cause an imbalance in the normal skin flora.
2. Should adhere to the skin aggressively during the dosing interval without its position being disturbed by activities such as bathing, exercise etc.
3. Should be easily removed.
4. Should not leave an unwashable residue on the skin.
5. Should have excellent (intimate) contact with the skin at macroscopic and microscopic level.

Backing Membrane:

Backing membranes are flexible and they provide a good bond to the drug reservoir, prevent drug from leaving the dosage form through the top, and accept printing. It is impermeable and protects the product during use on the skin e.g. metallic plastic laminate, plastic backing with absorbent pad and occlusive base plate (aluminum foil), adhesive foam pad (flexible polyurethane) with occlusive base plate (aluminum foil disc) etc.

Release Liner:

During storage release liner prevents the loss of the drug that has migrated into the adhesive layer and contamination. It is therefore regarded as a part of the primary packaging material rather than a part of dosage form for delivering the drug. The release liner is composed of a base layer which may be non-occlusive (paper fabric) or occlusive (polyethylene, polyvinylchloride) and a release coating layer made up of silicon or Teflon. Other materials used for TDDS release liner include polyester foil and metalized laminate.

APPROACHES FOR DEVELOPMENT OF TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS:[18-22]

Single layer drug in adhesive:

In this type the adhesive layer contains the drug. The adhesive layer not only serves to adhere the various layers together and also responsible for the releasing the drug to the skin. The adhesive layer is surrounded by a temporary liner and a backing.

Fig.3. Single layer drug in adhesive.

Matrix-dispersion system

In this type the drug is dispersed homogenously in a hydrophilic or lipophilic polymer matrix. This drug containing polymer disk is fixed on to an occlusive base plate in a compartment fabricated from a drug impermeable backing layer. Instead of applying the adhesive on the face of the drug reservoir. It is spread along with the circumference to form a strip of adhesive rim.[2]

Fig.4. Matrix-dispersion system.

Microreservoir Dissolution-Controlled TDD Systems:

This type of the delivery system can be considered a hybrid of the reservoir and matrix dispersion type delivery systems. In this approach the drug reservoir is formed by first suspending the drug solids in an aqueous solution of a water-miscible drug solubilizer, e.g., polyethylene glycol, and then homogeneously dispersing the drug suspension, with controlled aqueous solubility, in a lipophilic polymer, by high shear mechanical force, to form thousands of unleachable microscopic drug reservoirs. This thermodynamically unstable dispersion is quickly stabilized by immediately cross-linking the polymer chain in situ, which produces a medicated polymer disc with a constant surface area and a fixed thickness .

Ex: Nitrodisc system.

Fig.5. Microreservoir Dissolution-Controlled TDD Systems.

Drug Reservoir-in-Adhesive

In this system the drug reservoir is embedded between an impervious backing layer and a rate controlling membrane. The drug releases only through the rate controlling membrane, which can be micro porous or non porous. In the drug reservoir compartment, the drug can be in the form of a solution, suspension, gel or dispersed in a solid polymer matrix. Hypoallergenic adhesive polymer can be applied as outer surface polymeric membrane which is compatible with drug.

Fig.6. Drug Reservoir-in-Adhesive.

PREPARATION OF TRANSDERMAL PATCHES:[23-31]**Aluminium Backed Adhesive Film Method:**

Transdermal drug delivery system may produce unstable matrices if the loading dose is greater than 10 mg. Aluminium backed adhesive film method is a suitable one. For preparation of same, chloroform is choice of solvent, because most of the drugs as well as adhesive are soluble in chloroform. The drug is dissolved in chloroform and adhesive material will be added to the drug solution and dissolved. A custom made aluminum former is lined with aluminum foil and the ends blanked off with tightly fitting cork blocks.

Asymmetric TPX Membrane Method:

A prototype patch can be fabricated by a heat sealable polyester film (type 1009, 3m) with a concave of 1cm diameter used as the backing membrane. Drug sample is dispensed into the concave membrane, covered by a TPX {poly (4-methyl-1-pentene)} asymmetric membrane, and sealed by an adhesive.

Circular Teflon Mould Method:

Solutions containing polymers in various ratios are used in an organic solvent. Calculated amount of drug is dissolved in half the quantity of same organic solvent. Plasticizer added into drug polymer solution. The total contents are to be stirred and then poured into a circular teflon mould. And rate of solvent vaporization controlled with placing inverted glass funnel on teflon mould. The solvent is allowed to evaporate for 24 hrs. The dried films are to be stored in a desiccators.

Glass Substrate Method:

The polymeric solutions are kept a side for swelling then required quantity of plasticizer and drug solution are added and stirred for 10 min. Further, it is set-a side for some time to exclude any entrapped air and is then poured in a clean and dry anumbra petriplate. The rate of solvent evaporation is controlled by inverting a glass funnel over the petriplate. After over night, the dried films are taken out and stored in a desiccators.

EVALUATION OF TRANSDERMAL DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEM-[32-35]**EVALUATION OF ADHESIVE:****Peel adhesion test**

In this test, the force required to remove an adhesive coating from a test substrate is referred to as peel adhesion. Molecular weight of adhesive polymer, the type and amount of additives are the variables that determined the peel adhesion properties. A single tape is applied to a stainless steel plate or a backing membrane of choice and then tape is pulled from the substrate at a 180° angle, and the force required for tape removed is measured.

Fig.7. Peel adhesion test.

Tack properties

1. Thumb tack test
2. Rolling ball tack test
3. Quick stick (peel tack) test
4. Probe tack test

Thumb tack test:

It is a qualitative test applied for tack property determination of adhesive. The thumb is simply pressed on the adhesive and the relative tack property is detected.

Rolling ball tack test:

This test measures the softness of a polymer that relates to tack. In this test, stainless steel ball of 7/16 inches in diameter is released on an inclined track so that it rolls down and comes into contact with horizontal, upward facing adhesive. The distance the ball travels along the adhesive provides the measurement of tack, which is expressed in inch.

Fig.8 . Rolling ball tack test.

Quick Stick (peel-tack) test:

In this test, the tape is pulled away from the substrate at 90°C at a speed of 12 inches/min. The peel force required to break the bond between adhesive and substrate is measured and recorded as tack value, which is expressed in ounces or grams per inch width.

Fig.9. Quick Stick (peel-tack) test.

Probe Tack test:

In this test, the tip of a clean probe with a defined surface roughness is brought into contact with adhesive, and when a bond is formed between probe and adhesive. The subsequent removal of the probe mechanically breaks it. The force required to pull the probe away from the adhesive at fixed rate is recorded as tack and it is expressed in grams.

Fig.10 . Probe Tack test.

IN VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDIES

1. In these studies, excised skin is mounted on skin permeation cells.
2. Skin of hairless mouse is rather than human cadaver skin.
3. In-vitro system should be designed in such away that the intrinsic rate of release or permeation which is theoretically independent of the in-vitro design can be accurately determined.
4. Several designs of the in-vitro membrane permeation apparatus are in existence.
E.g. valia-chien (v-c) cell, keshary-chien(k-c) cell.

keshary-chien(k-c) cell:

It has an effective receptor volume 12 ml and a skin surface area of 3.14cm². The receptor solution is stirred by a star-head magnet rotating at a constant speed of 600 rpm driven by 3 W synchronous motor.

keshary-chien(k-c) cell.

IN-VIVO STUDIES:

In-vivo evaluations are the true depiction of the drug performance. The variables which cannot be taken into account during *in-vitro* studies can be fully explored during *in-vivo* studies. *In-vivo* evaluation of TDDS can be carried out using: Animal models
Human volunteers

Animal models:

The most common animal species used for evaluating transdermal drug delivery system are mouse, hairless rat, hairless dog, hairless rhesus monkey, rabbit, guinea pig etc.

Human models:

The final stage of the development of a transdermal device involves collection of pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic data following application of the patch to human volunteers. Clinical trials have been conducted to assess the efficacy, risk involved, side effects, patient compliance etc.

STABILITY STUDIES:

Stability studies are to be conducted according to the ICH guidelines by storing the TDDS samples at 40±0.5°C and 75±5% RH for 6 months. The samples were withdrawn at 0, 30, 60, 90 and 180 days and analyze suitably for the drug content.

SKIN IRRITATION STUDY:

Skin irritation and sensitization testing can be performed on healthy rabbits (average weight 1.2 to 1.5 kg). The dorsal surface (50cm²) of the rabbit is to be cleaned and remove the hair from the clean dorsal surface by shaving and clean the surface by using rectified spirit and the representative formulations can be applied over the skin. The patch is to be removed after 24 hr and the skin is to be observed and classified into 5 grades on the basis of the severity of skin injury.

LIMITATIONS:[36-41]

1. The drug moiety must possess some physicochemical properties for penetration through skin and if dose of drug is large i.e. more than 10-25mg/day transdermal delivery is very difficult. daily dose of drug preferred less than 5mg/day.
2. Local irritation at the site of administration such as itching, erythema and local edema may be caused by drug or the excipients used in the formulations.
3. Clinical need is another area that has to be examined carefully before a decision is made to develop a transdermal product.
4. Some patients develop contact dermatitis at the site of application due to system components.
5. The barrier function of the skin changes from one site to another, from person to person and with age.
6. Poor skin permeability limits the number of drugs that can be delivered in this manner.
7. A high drug level cannot achieve by this system.
8. Transdermal drug delivery is unable to deliver ionic drugs.
9. Transdermal drug delivery system is restricted to potent drug.
10. It cannot deliver drugs in a pulsatile fashion.
11. Tolerance inducing drugs or those (e.g., hormones) requiring chronopharmacological management is not suitable candidates.
12. Required significant lag time.
13. Drug molecule having large molecular size (>1000Dalton) cannot developed for transdermal deliver.

CONCLUSION

Transdermal drug delivery is a painless, convenient, and potentially effective way to deliver regular doses of many medications. Wide range of drugs can be delivered improved drug uptake Minimal complications and side effects low cost and easy to use. Due to the recent advances in technology and the incorporation of the drug to the site of action without rupturing the skin membrane transdermal route is becoming the most widely accepted route of drug administration. However, the transdermal technologies have limitations due to the relatively impermeable thick of outer stratum corneum layer. Researchers are trying to overcome this hurdle of poor permeability by physical and chemical means.

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ABBRIATIONS

TDDS	: Transdermal drug delivery system
GIT	: Gastro-Intestinal Track
U.S.F.D.A	: United States Food and drug administration
ICH	: International Conference on Harmonization
TPX	: poly (4-methyl-1-pentene)} asymmetric membrane
k-c cell	: keshary-chien(k-c) cell

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